

First record of *Chondrina clienta* (Westerlund, 1883) from Bohemia (Czech Republic)

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The occurrence of land snail *Chondrina clienta* (Westerlund, 1883) (Gastropoda: Chondrinidae) from Bohemia (Czech Republic) is reported for the first time.

So far, the land snail *Chondrina clienta* has been known within the Czech Republic only from Moravia (LOŽEK 1956, JUŘIČKOVÁ et al. 2001). This East Alpine and Southeast European snail is restricted to limestone rocks. In other parts of its range it occurs occasionally on walls and buildings (CAMERON 2003). In the Czech Republic it is common only in the Moravian Karst Protected Landscape Area (PLA) and Pálava PLA. The remaining known distribution is limited to four isolated sites (Fig. 1). Recently, a new isolated site has been discovered in the Rychlebské Hory Mts (JUŘIČKOVÁ et al., 2005). This new site is an old limestone quarry and the circumstances of the species occurrence indicate a non-native spreading in the recent time.

Locality and material examined: E Bohemia, Luže village (49°53'05.8" N, 16°01'55.8" E, mapping grid – 6162), on a wall of Košumberk castle, 360 m a.s.l., 15 August 2004, one living adult specimen, J. Novák and M. Novák leg. and coll., M. Horsák det. This is the first finding from a castle on non-limestone bedrock within the Czech Republic. Košumberk castle is another distributional extension of this species toward the northwest, like the limestone quarry in the Rychlebské Hory Mts. Both these occurrences seem to be non-native and they may document new spreading of *Chondrina clienta* in the recent time.

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Fig. 1. Present distribution of *Chondrina clienta* in the Czech Republic; broken line shows the historical border between Bohemia and Moravia. Black dot – current populations, empty dot – extinct populations, black square – the first record in Bohemia. The map was adopted from JUŘIČKOVÁ et al. (2005).